

emotions

BOARD GAME

EMOTIONS BOARD GAME INSTRUCTIONS:

Shuffle and place the cards face down in a stack so that all players can reach them. Cards with orange color ask questions related to emotional awareness, as in “How would you feel if ...”, while cards with purple color ask questions related to emotional self-regulation, as in “What would you do if ...”.

Each team chooses a pawn and places it in the START square. The team with the lowest roll plays first.

When a team’s pawn lands on a question mark, the other team draws a card and reads out loud the question, which must then be answered by the players of the first team.

If the pawn lands on a square with an arrow, it moves forward or goes back as many squares as the arrow indicates.

When a team’s pawn lands on a square with an exclamation mark, its players must answer a question related to emotional awareness or self-regulation, created by the other team’s players.

The team whose pawn reaches the FINISH square second wins!

